

The Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectra of Cinnamylidene Arylamines

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A comparison of the chemical properties of carbonyl and imine functions has been well explored. The spectral properties of these functions in comparison to each other have also been reported¹. Recently the effect of conjugation as manifested in I.R. and U.V. spectroscopy has been described in enones and conjugated imines². In this report we have described the N.M.R. spectra of few conjugated imines.

The imines described here were prepared as described earlier³. The N.M.R. spectra (60 MHz in CDCl₃) of cinnamylidene arylamines is recorded in Table I and of α -bromo cinnamylidene arylamine in Table II. The observations recorded in these tables indicate high deshielding of olefinic protons and these olefinic protons are merged with aromatic protons. This novel high deshielding could be assigned to anisotropic effect of phenyl conjugated azomethine group. However, the parent aldehyde from which these imines have been obtained shows up olefinic protons in the region 3–4 τ as clean two doublets. The olefinic protons could not be resolved even at a high resolution of 220 MHz (Table I, Sr. No. V). The solvent benzene is found to induce solvent shift in systems of the types (I) and (II)³.

Therefore, it was thought worth while to record the N.M.R. spectrum (220 MHz in C₆D₆) of cinnamylidene *m*-chloroaniline in order to determine the conformation of the diene (Table I, Sr. No. VII). As a result of the solvent shift criteria the olefinic protons came up in the olefinic region and the parameters obtained could enable to make the assignment to the diene portion as indicated here :

$$H_a = 3.37\tau$$

$$H_b = 3.0\tau$$

$$H_c = 2.09\tau$$

$$J_{ab} = 16.2\text{Hz}$$

$$J_{ac} = 0.0\text{Hz}$$

$$J_{bc} = 9.0\text{Hz}$$

1. R. W. Layer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, 463.
2. N. Singh, J. S. Sandhu and Suresh Mohan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 185.
3. J. Ranayne and D. H. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc. (c)* 1967, 2642; *ibid.*, B, 1967, 540.

TABLE I

X	H_a	H_b	H_d	H_e	H_f	H_c	H_g	H_h	Instrument
1. <i>m</i> -CH ₃ ^h		2.7, 7H(m)		2.9, 4H(d)		1.8, 1H(q)		7.7, 3H(s)	Varian 60
2. <i>p</i> -F			2.80, 11H(m)			1.90, 1H(t)		—	
3. <i>p</i> -COCH ₃		2.9, 11H(m)				1.8, 1H(t)		—	60 Mc/s in CDCl ₃ .
4. H		2.75, 12H(m)				1.85, 1H(t)		—	HR-220
5. <i>m</i> -Cl		2.75, 12H(m)				1.8, 1H(t)		—	HR-220
6. <i>m</i> -Cl		2.70, 11H(m)				1.8, 1H(s)		—	220 Mc/s, HR in CDCl ₃
7. <i>m</i> -Cl		3.35, 2H(d)	2.9, 9H(m)			2.1, 1H(d)		—	220 Mc/s, HR in C ₆ D ₆

TABLE II

X	H_a	H_b	H_d	H_e	H_f	H_c	H_g	H_h	Instrument
1. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ ^h		2.7, 6H(m)		2.9, 4H(d)		1.8, 1H(q)	—	7.7, 3H(s)	Varian 60
2. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ ^h		2.7, 6H(m)		2.9, 4H(d)		1.8, 1H(q)	—	7.7, 3H(s)	
3. <i>p</i> -Cl			2.80, 10H(m)			1.90, 1H(t)	—	—	60 Mc/s in CDCl ₃
4. <i>p</i> -Br			2.65, 6H(m)	2.9, 4H(m)		1.85, 1H(t)	—	—	
5. <i>p</i> -OCH ₂ ^g CH ₃ ^h				2.9, 10H(m)		1.8, 1H(q)	6.1, 2H(q)	8.65, 3H(t)	

This solvent induced shift in case of imines does not seem to have been recorded earlier. Further studies of solvent induced shift are under active investigation. The work is also in progress to know the conformation of phenyl rings.

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